

ISic1472

I.Sicily inscription 1472

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.07

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Piazza della Vittoria, in reuse in Hellenistic house west of the
Fountain house

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μεγάλας [Θεᾶς]

Apparatus

Text after Dubois

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 285070

EDR 107987

EDCS 64900710

PHI 330713

Bibliography

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